

OSCAR

Open Science Clusters' Action
for Research & Society

Clusters' Services and Data Sources Portfolios

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DELIVERABLE ABSTRACT

The aim of this deliverable: ***D2.1 Clusters’ Services and Data Sources Portfolios***, carried out in the framework of **WP2: Composable Research Infrastructure Services in EOSC** of the [OSCARS Open Science Clusters’ Action for Research and Society project](#), was to catalogue, evaluate and undertake a gap analysis of the Services and FAIR Data resources offered by the five [Science Clusters](#) in the domains of [Astronomy and Particle Physics](#), [Environmental Science](#), [Life Science](#), [Photon and Neutron Science](#) and [Social Sciences and Humanities](#). This work was undertaken in the context of the emerging [EOSC Federation](#), where the Science Clusters and their related Research Infrastructures play a crucial role. The deliverable covers the initial versions of the Cluster catalogues, their mapping, consolidation and transition to *Services and Data Source Portfolios*, as well as an initial exploration of potential *Composability Scenarios* for each of the Clusters. The final goal of the deliverable was to highlight possible common approaches, foster knowledge exchange between the Science Clusters and identify where the EOSC services can facilitate the composability of these offerings. This deliverable provides a solid foundation for the remaining work on *composability* and *engagement* which will be continued in WP2.

TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
Cluster	See: Science Cluster
Competence	“Competence is a demonstrated ability to apply knowledge, skills and attributes for achieving desirable results”, as per the European e-Competence Framework definition. (Source: OSCARS D1.1)
CODAS	Composable Open Data and Analysis Services

Composability	Refers to the ability to combine and integrate smaller, modular components or services into more complex systems. In a composable system, each component is designed to function independently but can be easily assembled or reconfigured with others to create new workflows or applications.
ELIXIR	Life Sciences Research Infrastructure for life science data
ENVRI	Environmental Research Infrastructures Cluster (Source: OSCARS D4.3)
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
ERA	European Research Area
ESCAPE	Astronomy and Particle Physics Research Infrastructures Cluster (Source: OSCARS D4.3)
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
FAIR data	Data that is Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Re-usable (See for example: FAIR Principles)
HPC	High-performance computing
LS-RI	European Life-Sciences Research Infrastructures (Source: OSCARS D1.1)
MP	Market place
MS	Milestone
NaaVRE	Notebook-as-a-VRE
OOCP	OSCARS Open Call Projects
OSCARS	Open Science Clusters' Action for Research and Society, the name of the project that this deliverable contributes to.
Open Science	Is the movement to make scientific research and its dissemination accessible to all levels of society. (Source: OSCARS D1.1)
PaNOSC	Photon and Neutron Open Science Cluster (Source: OSCARS D1.1)
RI	Research Infrastructure
Science Cluster	The Science Clusters are a group of Research Infrastructures (RIs) related through the domain of science on which they operate. There are five Science Clusters (Source: OSCARS D1.1)
Service	A service is an activity that performs an action on someone's demand. Somebody has to take care of it. A service is based on a software.
Software	Software is a digital object.
SSHOC	Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cluster
SSHOMP	Social Sciences and Humanities Open Marketplace

VRE	A Virtual Research Environment is defined as an environment that allows a researcher to provide/select data and execute a workflow (in a workflow engine).
Workflow	A well defined series of tasks.
WP	Work package

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Executive summary

OSCARS (Open Science Clusters' Action for Research and Society) is a four-year Horizon Europe project, which aims to foster the uptake of Open Science in Europe by mapping and where possible consolidating the achievements of world-class European research infrastructures on the ESFRI roadmap and beyond into lasting interdisciplinary FAIR data services, tools and working practices. The project will strengthen the role of the five Science Clusters in the European Research Area by developing domain-specific Competence Centres and by fostering the implementation of Open Science Projects and services funded through a cascading grant mechanism.

The purpose of this document is to highlight the achievements within the Consolidation Task 2.1, which focuses on the mapping, creation, refinement, and exploitation of a **Services and Data Sources Portfolio**, while considering the different starting points of the involved Science Clusters. As part of Task 2.1, each of the five Clusters has developed an extensive list of research resources, accompanied by a brief list of flagship services promoting their key services. The finalisation of the first full version portfolio is a major outcome of the Consolidation Workshop, which also served to define the most important terms with respect to workflow of services in a cross-cluster sense.

Additionally, each Cluster presents two scientific scenarios that are typical for their field of research. These examples include services and data sources from the Cluster's portfolio, which have great potential for composability. The Clusters discussed and agreed that within the OSCARS project framework, that composability refers to the ability to combine and integrate smaller, modular components or services into more complex systems. In a composable system, each component is designed to function independently, but can be easily adapted or reconfigured with others to create new workflows or applications. The descriptions of these initial scenarios will provide a basis for further development as part of Task 2.2, including identified improvements which will need to be made to the selected services to enable their composability.

1. Introduction

As [outlined](#) by the European Commission, the ambition of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is to provide European researchers with a federated and open multi-disciplinary environment where they can publish, find and reuse data, tools and services for research, innovation and educational purposes. This deliverable finalises Task 2.1 with the focus on consolidation. The first aim of this task is to create a catalogue of ‘the Services and FAIR Data portfolios offered by each of the Clusters’. Secondly, a gap analysis intends to identify where these ‘offerings’ may be made composable. Thirdly, the task targets to ‘highlight possible common approaches and to foster knowledge exchange between the Science Clusters’. And finally, ‘identify where the EOSC Core and Exchange services can facilitate the composability of these offerings’.

The creation of the catalogue requires different levels of work for each Cluster, as the initial status of the Clusters varied strongly. While the description of the task explicitly refers to the EOSC Marketplace, this was deprecated in April 2024, shortly after the start of the OSCARS project, as part of the transition to the [EOSC EU Node](#). Luckily, the underlying data could be stored in a [data dump](#) with the intent to revive it later and to facilitate machine-searchable access. A selected part of this data has been ingested into the [SSH Open Marketplace](#). The initial versions of the catalogues were published within MS3, see Section [2](#).

The second and third aims were the identification of common approaches and the knowledge exchange between the Clusters. These aims were achieved during the [Consolidation and Terminology Workshop](#), held from 30 September to 2 October 2024 in Hamburg (MS4). The various outcomes of the in-depth discussions are presented in Section [3](#). These results also determined the further work on the catalogues with respect to the ‘Final Version of the Portfolio’ (MS5). During the continuous work, we realised that these catalogues should be living documents, instead of having a final version as described in the OSCARS project proposal, see Section [4](#). The fourth aim was the identification of EOSC Core and Exchange services that can facilitate the composability of the resources. This aim was adapted to focus on the newly established [EOSC Resource Hub](#) (available since November 2024).

Finally, OSCARS is, at its core, a collaborative initiative aiming to unify efforts and underscore the synergies across the five Science Clusters. The project strives to consolidate and harmonise their contributions to EOSC and foster interdisciplinary engagement, and the uptake of Open Science practices by researchers. It is essential that the work undertaken in OSCARS WP2 responds to the needs of the researchers who will discover, use and in the future compose the services and data sources identified by the Science Clusters for their day-to-day work. In collaboration with the Clusters’ RIs and research communities, and in liaison with the projects funded under the OSCARS Open Calls, a researcher-centred approach is crucial to the success of this work.

2. Towards an initial version of the Cluster Catalogues

The creation of the catalogues requires different levels of work for each Cluster, as their initial status varies considerably. Some of the Clusters (SSHOC, ESCAPE and ENVRI) already had a central landing page to explore existing services and data sources, while the others (LS-RI, PaNOSC) had to map these services from several, non-centralised resources. The following sections serve to introduce the starting points of each Cluster and also their path towards the initial version of their portfolios.

2.1. PaNOSC Starting Point

Before the start of the OSCARS project, the Photon and Neutron Open Science Cluster (PaNOSC) only had limited central collections of resources. In addition to the EOSC marketplace (recommended in the proposal), only the [PaNdata Software Catalogue](#) is worth mentioning. This catalogue, however, only lists software, but no services and data sources and thus could not serve as sole source of information. Moreover, the PaNdata Software Catalogue was largely moribund, with most information being out-of-date. The recommended EOSC marketplace contained the full range of resources that are of interest for the intended portfolio. Unfortunately, it only contained three services and eight data sources with a loose connection to PaN research. Consequently, the portfolio had to be created from the ground up. A manual search started with link collections on the most relevant institutions of PaNOSC, i.e. the RIs within [LEAPS](#), [LENS](#), and [CERIC](#), as well as [IUCr](#). During the search, the focus was on resources from European organisations, with Open Access, and with PaN-specific context. Nonetheless, resources outside these requirements were not excluded initially, especially when they seemed to play a unique and important role within the community. The properties listed for each resource were based on the ones used in the various EOSC marketplace profiles in order to reuse established ideas and to facilitate a potential unification with the data dump.

The [initial version](#) of the PaNOSC portfolio for MS3 included 190 services, 107 data sources, and 157 pieces of software.

2.2. SSHOC Starting Point

Several methods were considered to build the Social Sciences and Humanities Open Cluster (SSHOC) portfolio of services and data sources.

Initially, and building on EOSC onboarding efforts as they were defined between 2019 and 2023, a number of resources related to the SSHOC Cluster were added to the now closed EOSC catalogue and Marketplace. All metadata from the EOSC Catalogue were made

accessible via a curated [data dump](#). An experiment was conducted to understand how to best identify the SSHOC relevant resources from this dump. Among the 463 services documented in this EOSC data dump – 64 services being data sources – several approaches were considered for obtaining a subset of services relevant to a given Science Cluster. Three possible approaches (or perimeters) were investigated:

1. List of services based on the **cluster tag**. As part of the EOSC-Future project, cluster tags were created and have been manually added to the services onboarded. Although based on manual efforts of the EOSC-Future team and of some service providers, without clear or strict guidelines for collective tagging of the resources, filtering using this parameter allows for a first view of the Science Clusters' portfolios.
2. List of services based on **providers' names**. Providers included under each Cluster are restricted to known partners from the OSCARS project (WP2). For a more complete overview, each Cluster should provide a defined list of partner institutions that should be mapped to the provider profiles included in the EOSC data dump.
3. List of services based on **disciplines**. This approach assumes that a set of disciplines (according to the disciplines listed in the related EOSC vocabulary) can be affiliated to each Science Cluster. This "disciplinary affiliation" is not an easy task and should be discussed and agreed among the other Clusters should they be interested in following that path to identify resources relevant to their Cluster's perimeter.

After merging the results obtained thanks to these three approaches, a refined list of 65 SSHOC services and data sources was produced.

A second approach when building the SSHOC portfolio was to **rely on the discovery portal of the Cluster, the [SSH Open Marketplace](#)** that listed the [services and data sources](#) that resulted from the SSHOC project.

Finally, another line of work, investigated by the SSHOC Cluster members since 2022, is the possibility for each partner to select a handful of services (2–3) to bring them into the Cluster portfolio. That way, only a limited number of resources – termed the flagships – would be included in the portfolio.

Each of these approaches/methodologies require the Cluster to balance exhaustivity and selectivity in the definition of the perimeter of the portfolio.

2.3. ENVRI Starting Point

Before the start of the OSCARS project, the ENVRI Cluster for Environmental Sciences already had a structured service portfolio thanks to the [ENVRI-Hub](#). Key components included:

- **Service Catalogue:** A robust collection of individual RI services covering diverse domains like atmospheric sciences, biodiversity, and marine ecosystems. Examples include catalogues from [LifeWatch](#), [eLTER](#), [ICOS](#), [SeaDataNet](#), and [EuroArgo](#)..
- **Knowledge Base and Search Engine:** An advanced search tool for discovering services, datasets, and metadata across participating RIs, ensuring data is FAIR and accessible.
- **Training Catalogue:** A curated repository of educational resources, workshops, and training programs tailored to improve competencies in data management and analysis.
- **Interface to Virtual Research Environments (VREs):** Tools like [Notebook-as-a-VRE \(NaaVRE\)](#) provide access to computational workflows, enabling researchers to analyze datasets interactively.
- **Cloud and RI Integration:** Established interfaces to connect underlying research infrastructures and cloud resources for seamless service provisioning.

Approach for Portfolio Consolidation

The ENVRI Cluster adopted a systematic approach to enhance and consolidate its portfolio for Task 2.1:

1. **Leveraging Existing Resources:** The portfolio builds on existing assets from ENVRI-FAIR, ensuring continuity, leveraging past investments and encouraging sustainability.
2. **Service Identification:**
 - The primary source of information for the portfolio was the [ENVRI-Hub service catalogue](#).
 - Additional resources were identified from RI-specific catalogues, such as LifeWatch and ICOS, and integrated into the broader ENVRI portfolio.
3. **Alignment with EOSC Goals:** Each service and dataset was assessed for alignment with EOSC Core and Exchange principles, focusing on FAIR compliance and composability.
4. **Gap Analysis:** The ENVRI Cluster conducted a thorough review to identify areas where services could be enhanced for greater interoperability and composability. This included the standardization of metadata, APIs, and the adoption of machine-actionable workflows.

Initial Portfolio for MS3

The initial ENVRI portfolio for MS3 encompassed:

- **Services:** A diverse array of tools and applications tailored to the environmental sciences community, including analytical platforms, data visualization tools, and FAIR compliance frameworks.
- **Data Sources:** Key datasets spanning climate variables, biodiversity metrics, and oceanographic observations.
- **Training Resources:** A broad selection of training materials and interactive modules available through the Training Catalogue.

Key Challenges

- **Heterogeneity of RIs:** ENVRI's services span a wide range of domains, requiring significant effort to standardize data formats and metadata across infrastructures.
- **Integration with EOSC:** Ensuring seamless interoperability with EOSC Core and Exchange while maintaining the unique value of ENVRI services.
- **Engagement with Smaller RIs:** Supporting less-resourced infrastructures to onboard services and datasets into the ENVRI-Hub.

2.4. LS-RI Starting Point

Building and formalisation of the Life Sciences Research Infrastructure (LS-RI) Cluster with the LS-RI community across domains, was initiated and strengthened through projects such as BioMedBridges, [CORBEL](#) and [EOSC-Life](#). Each of these consortia activated implementation and development of a spectrum of LS-RI services, however, not all LS-RIs' services or resources are currently linked to shared common registries and platforms. The initial [LS-RI website](#) developed in CORBEL served as a shared platform with a general overview on the services portfolio in individual Life Science RIs (experimental and computational scientific services) and redirecting to individual RI websites and platforms. Common registries and solutions around handling data, data services, computational tools and FAIR guidelines in the life science domain were co-developed and populated with support through the EOSC-Life cluster project that brought together 13 LS-RIs communities. The key-outcomes were made publicly available on the EOSC-Life project website, LS RIs websites, and summarised in the EOSC-Life consortium publication "*Be Sustainable: EOSC-Life Recommendations for Implementation of FAIR Principles in Life Science Data Handling*" ([David et al., 2024](#)). A partial catalogue, presented as a [collection of FAIR EOSC-Life data resources](#), is hosted on the

FAIRsharing platform. This catalogue includes contributions from EOSC-Life partners, representing over 100 diverse data resources, which collectively provide access to thousands of databases, standards and policies for LS Network.

2.5. ESCAPE Starting Point

The [ESCAPE project](#) included High Energy and Nuclear Physics, Astroparticle Physics, and Astronomy research infrastructures. Its services are therefore tested on highly complex and large-scale datasets. The initial version of the ESCAPE portfolio was built based on the key high-level results achieved during the [ESCAPE project](#) in addition to some services of recognised utility already in use in the community and operated by individual components of the Cluster. The initial version of the ESCAPE portfolio for MS3 included ten services and one main data source.

3. Consolidation of the Cluster Portfolios

Following up the initial version of the Services and Data Source Portfolio (OSCARS MS3), in which each Cluster catalogues their relevant [Services and Data Sources](#), a [Consolidation workshop](#) (OSCARS MS4) was organised by WP2 in order to discuss challenges and solutions encountered by the Science Clusters in developing their portfolios.

For each Cluster, key Service and Data Source contacts were identified and invited to join the discussions during the workshop. The initial idea was that, ideally, three roles within each Cluster could be represented: a **Portfolio Manager**, a **Technical Manager** and a **Strategic Manager**. Gathering 17 participants in an hybrid format – in-person in Hamburg at the DESY premises and online – the Cluster representatives were tasked to update their services and data sources portfolio, taking into account the following questions:

- *What is the status of your Cluster portfolio?* Considering the variety of methods that can be used to create a Cluster portfolio, how would you describe your Cluster services and data sources inventory?
- *What are the Services presenting a composability potential?* Identify and select a set of services which, when improved, will provide the basis for their Composable Open Data and Analysis Services (CODAS).
- *What could be a good demonstrator for your Cluster?* Are there any existing ideas that your Cluster plans to build upon to develop the OSCARS composability demonstrators?
- Which challenges or obstacles are you encountering working on these questions?

All Clusters answered these questions in presentations with subsequent discussions. The results are summarised in Table 1.

Table 1. – Brief summary of the portfolio status of the individual Clusters, including potentials and challenges.

Science Cluster	Portfolio status	Composability potential of services	Potential demonstrators	Challenges
SSHOC	Several methods to develop the SSHOC portfolio: from the EOSC data dump ; from the SSH Open Marketplace (MP) and SSHOC project results list of resources; renewing the flagship services idea. Updates with	Flagship services idea to cater to different audiences/needs. Main question leading the work: which composability scenarios to push for SSHOC?	Proposal is to use the SSHOC MP for the narrative part of the workflows Use of Named Entity Recognition (NER) for different use cases, e.g. Named Entity Linking or for the	Offering resources / workflows that cater to differing levels of digital literacy. How to relate our work on the service and data portfolio to the bigger EOOSC picture?

Science Cluster	Portfolio status	Composability potential of services	Potential demonstrators	Challenges
	new training and services		anonymisation of interviews	
PANOSC	<p>Apart from the PaNdata Software Catalogue, no marketplace or comparable collection available before OSCARS, Building up portfolio largely from scratch</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ 190 services ■ 160 software ■ 110 data sources 	<p>VRE Data Transfer Workflows Software Data Formats</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Data download from doi ■ PaN Data Lake using EOSC Data transfer service 	<p>Agreeing on common solutions with other Clusters for:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Software catalogue ■ Software ■ Ontologies ■ Workflows ■ Data Formats ■ Training <p>The risk that composability becomes too abstract and does not help scientists</p>
ENVRI	<p>The ENVRI-Hub includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ A catalogue: https://envrihub.v.m.fedcloud.eu/cse/rvicesmain ■ Knowledge Base and Search Engine ■ Training (catalogue) ■ Interface to VRE ■ Interface to underlying RI and Cloud 	<p>High potential for composability through:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Standardised metadata and data formats across participating RIs. ■ Federated APIs enabling interoperability between RI services. ■ Harmonisation of workflows for climate data, biodiversity studies, and ocean monitoring. ■ Support for machine-actionable tools and scientific knowledge graphs (SKGs). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Data integration for Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) using the VRE. ■ Multi-source biodiversity monitoring integrating LifeWatch, ICOS, and eLTER data. ■ Harmonized metadata and workflow reproducibility for ecosystem monitoring. ■ Interactive climate modeling workflows utilizing federated datasets and NaaVRE tools. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Ensuring interoperability across diverse RIs and data sources. ■ Adopting composability standards that balance complexity with usability. ■ Maintaining consistent quality across datasets and services. ■ Engaging smaller, less-structured communities in adopting FAIR principles. ■ Long-term sustainability of federated infrastructure and tools.
ESCAPE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Distributed Data Management ■ Analysis Framework for 	Rucio FTS3	CERN VRE & Jupyter Hub	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ paradigm shift ■ flexibility ■ authentication

Science Cluster	Portfolio status	Composability potential of services	Potential demonstrators	Challenges
	Scientific Computing <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Interoperability Framework for Data and Services ■ Preservation and re-interpretation of analysis workflows and results 	Content Delivery and Latency Hiding mechanisms HiPS ESAP VRE Virtual Observatory Zenodo OSST REANA Citizen Science	Cherenkov Telescope Array (CTAO)	
LS-RI (EOSC-Life)	The LS-RI Cluster is in the process of establishing a comprehensive registry connecting or redirecting to a portfolio of services and data resources tailored to life sciences research. (David et al., 2025 paper in prep). For example, building on the collection of FAIR EOSC-Life data resources hosted on the FAIRsharing platform.	AAI Crosswalk and mapping Data annotation Data curation Data mobilisation Data storage FAIRification support Interoperability tools and framework (LOST) Repositories Service badging Software Standards VRE Sensitive Data handling. Please note: that this list is not exhaustive	FAIR data management and research collaboration: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ MOLGENIS ■ FAIRDOM-SE EK ■ ELIXIR AAI for secure data access. ■ RDMKit ■ Identifiers.org for unique dataset identification ■ WorkflowHub ■ RO-Crate ■ Sensitive Data Toolbox ■ Covid19 Data Portal (see also: EOSC-Life Open Calls and Demonstrators) Please note: that this list is not exhaustive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ■ Definition and Consensus ■ Awareness and Community Engagement ■ Governance Complexity ■ Incentives for FAIR and Open Science Practices ■ Funding and Policy Alignment ■ Sustainability and Resource Allocation ■ Interoperability and Standardisation ■ Data Stewardship and Quality Control ■ Skills Development and Harmonisation ■ Storage and Infrastructure (David et al., 2025 paper in prep).

In addition, the participants discussed different perspectives to improve and unify the portfolios, including the services description (Sec. [Services Description](#)), the perimeter of the portfolio (Sec. [Perimeter of the Portfolio](#)), common terms used across the Clusters (Sec. [Cross-cluster Dimensions](#)), and a gap analysis (Sec. [Gap Analysis](#)).

3.1. Services Description

The best way to describe the portfolio resources was naturally one of the first questions discussed as part of the WP2 work. Some “generic” information was easily identified, especially following the data modelling and onboarding experiences from previous projects.¹ In particular by considering the [v4.00 of the EOSC Resource Profiles](#), we identified the metadata descriptors listed in Tab. 2 as mandatory in any service and data sources cataloguing efforts, while some of them led to discussion, as their use leads to open questions.

Table 2. – Main information fields the Science Clusters service description should include

Field name in the current Cluster portfolio	v4.00 of the EOSC Resource Profiles – field name equivalent	comments/ open questions
Full name	Name	
Institute	Resource Organisation	External identifier to use: ROR Importance to distinguish some roles. See for example Distinction between Resource Organisation and Resource Providers
Link	Webpage	
Description	Description	
Scientific domain	Scientific Domain	Scientific Subdomain also exists in the EOSC Profile, hierarchic vocabulary
keywords	Tags	Where the Cluster affiliation was sometimes recorded in the EOSC catalogue
Hosted in Europe?	Resource Geographic Location	
Order type (fully open access, open access, restricted, ...), e.g. COAR Access Rights	Order Type	
Type of software/resources	Category	TaDiRAH: covers a good share of tasks within PaN, but many unmapped tasks. Alternatives?
Technical Readiness Level (TRL)	Technology Readiness Level	Hard to determine, often developers don't know themselves. Alternatives mentioned during workshop: Business Readiness Level (BRL)

¹ From EOSC-Hub, to EOSC-Future with input and contributions from the five science cluster projects.

		Societal Readiness Level (SRL)
General or Cluster specific service? (more or less the scientific domain used in PaN currently)		In the new resource Hub, the distinction between “horizontal services” and others is kept

In general, the necessity to rely on and point to external identifiers is well-known to the five Science Clusters. For persons, the use of the [ORCID](#) is already widespread and recommended; for (hosting/developing) institutions [ROR](#) is recommended. And other research products, such as datasets, publications, software generally receive [DOIs](#) and/or handles.

In addition to identifiers, the use of established taxonomies and dictionaries is highly important. To describe the type of software in an appropriate way, different options were discussed. Finally, we decided to primarily use [TaDiRAH](#) terms, complemented by [EOSC Resource Categories](#). For the licences, the [SPDX License List](#) was used. This approach seems to be interesting for several of the Science Clusters.

3.2. Perimeter of the Portfolio

The ideal scope of the Science Clusters portfolio has been a key topic of discussion since the OSCARS project began. The challenge lies in striking a balance between comprehensiveness – listing all services and data sources relevant to the domains covered by a given Cluster – and defining the project’s boundaries. These boundaries could focus on resources provided exclusively by OSCARS project partners or limit the scope to a selected set of services intended for use in the composability demonstrators (T2.3). These options have been considered individually within each Cluster.

The approach might differ from one Science Cluster to another, but common criteria have also been identified to ensure a coherence between the approaches chosen by each Cluster:

- **Reliability of the service.** Beyond a strict definition/understanding of a high Technology Readiness Level (≥ 8), services included in a Cluster portfolio need to be reliable. This means that very specific services that are still maintained by a limited team but covering a niche and presenting a lower TRL can be included.
- **Level of maintenance.** If a service or software is no longer maintained any more, ‘nobody’ will be able to apply the necessary changes to make that tool composable with the other components envisioned in a scenario. Therefore, each Cluster should investigate the appropriate way to ensure that the upgrades needed to integrate the service in a larger environment are feasible.

- **Cross-clusters approach.** At least one composability scenario should include a cross-cluster dimension. The services included in the Cluster portfolio should already take that into consideration.
- **Balance.** Include both high impact- and base level services.

3.3. Cross-cluster Dimensions

Some key definitions were suggested by the workshop participants and a “generic” schema capturing the commonalities between the Clusters was produced (see Fig. 1).

- A *workflow* is a well defined series of tasks.
- *Composability* refers to the ability to combine and integrate smaller, modular components or services into more complex systems. In a composable system, each component is designed to function independently but can be easily assembled or reconfigured with others to create new workflows or applications.
- A *Virtual Research Environment (VRE)* is an environment or platform that allows a researcher to provide/select data and execute a workflow (in a workflow engine).

Figure 1 – An initial visualisation of a “Generic” schema of key definitions capturing the commonalities between the Clusters [source].

In addition to these consolidation dimensions, a presentation was given by the [AARC Tree](#) project establishing contact for potential collaborations regarding the AAI integration.

3.4. Gap Analysis

- In order to improve the findability of required services for the composability task: add category 'specialisation' with the fields 'generic' or 'cluster specific'
- Information gap in metadata with respect to softwares/services to receive the data (corrections, ...): keyword provenance
- TaDiRAH does not cover complete range of requested categories of service tasks: recommendation (while post processing the workshop) combination of [TaDiRAH](#) and [EOSC Resource Category](#)
- Maintenance level: is somebody currently taking care of the code? This person might be needed to perform minor changes to facilitate compatibility with other services; level hard to define, cannot be realised within task 2.1

4. Services and Data Source Portfolio

To enable the vision of the European Science Cloud (EOSC) as a federated and open multi-disciplinary environment where researchers can publish, find and reuse data, tools and services for research, innovation and educational purposes, strong portfolios of Services and Data Source Portfolios, for each Science Cluster, are needed.

The creation, curation, and maintenance over time of a service portfolio is seen by most of the Clusters as an evolving and iterative process, which means that the portfolio is a living document without a “Final Version”, as originally described in the OSCARS proposal. Therefore, we refrain from using the term ‘final version’. Additionally, the long-term sustainability of these portfolios, through Science Cluster catalogues, such as the [ENVRI-Hub](#) or the [SSH Open Marketplace](#), need to be considered.

During the OSCARS consolidation phase of the discussions (Sec. Consolidation), the Clusters highlighted and agreed that there is a need for each Cluster in OSCARS to choose a subset of services and FAIR data sources to expose the service offer to researchers. Further, the chosen subset facilitates the exploration of the potential of some services to become components of wider composability demonstrators (during the OSCARS project and beyond). Whether or not these portfolios should be published/released as Cluster service catalogues or how they would link to the Competence Centres (cf. WP1) is up to each Cluster. In addition, the way, in which the Clusters will operate in the EOSC Federation (as a node or not), and how the resources they provide, curate, or support can be onboarded to the EOSC Resource Hub and can be related to the EOSC-EU node is still an open question as long as the interoperability sections of the EOSC Federation Handbook are not agreed on.

The following paragraphs offer a view of what the Clusters’ Services and Data Source Portfolios currently look like and how it could evolve in the near future.

4.1. PaNOSC Portfolio

In comparison to the initial version, PaNOSC significantly improved its portfolio by different measures. First of all, the [PaNOSC Competence Center](#), consisting of representatives of the individual RIs, were asked to complement the portfolio in particular with regard to adding TRL and complementing missing tools. As a result, we could not only add 37 new services, 5 new software, 5 new data sources, but we also received valid information on the development status of software and services. In parallel, we improved the portfolio by using established taxonomies and dictionaries. For the licences, the [SPDX License List](#) was used. Further, we added the information on the related experimental method in the form of PaNET ID and PaNET term, which now allows for a quick filter for a specific technique. Within

PaNOSC, we decided not to include the markers “generic” and “cluster specific”, but to continue the use of the [EOSC Profile terms for the Scientific Domain](#). And for the type of software, we decided to primarily use [TaDiRAH](#) terms, complemented by [EOSC Resource Categories](#). This approach reduced the number of terms from 66 to 31, especially by excluding duplicates (e.g. analysis, analysing, analyzing). Further, eight previously uncategorized software and 25 services are now categorized. However, the unification of terms may have the disadvantage of losing the descriptive depth, e.g. programming is a very versatile term, with currently no subcategories in both taxonomies. An extension of the TaDiRAH taxonomy could solve this issue.

The following paragraphs highlight the key tools of the portfolio from different categories.

4.1.1. Catalogues of Data and Services (and Software)

- Most PaNOSC RI have their own **data storages for raw (and derived data)**. Access is only granted to the original researcher team, until an embargo period of typically 3 years has ended. The data sets might have a unique handle or doi.
- **Metadata Catalogues** are under development that will provide cross-facility access to FAIR data in the future: [iCAT](#) and [SciCat](#) (used at 5 and 8 RIs worldwide, respectively)
- The key results of PaN research are **atomic and molecular structures** that are stored in dedicated data bases, e.g. [Protein Data Bank](#), [Inorganic Crystal Structure Database](#)
- Relevant **software** is listed in the [PaNdata Software Catalogue](#).

4.1.2. Training Catalogue

- [Photon and Neutron Training](#)
- [FAIRsharing](#)

4.1.3. Knowledge Base and Search Engine

- [European PaN Open Data Search Portal](#) gives easy access to datasets from data sources of PaN RIs using the federated search engine compatible with [OpenAIRE](#).
- [WayForLight](#) provides a single entry point for information about the European synchrotrons and free electron lasers. Several search options facilitate to filter for the beamlines best suitable for an intended experiment.

4.1.4. Virtual Research Environment (VRE)

- [VISA](#) (Virtual Infrastructure for Scientific Analysis) creates compute instances on a RIs data analysis infrastructure to analyse experimental data using just a web browser.

4.1.5. Quality Guidelines and Tools

See Training Catalogues

4.1.6. Advanced Analytics Framework

- The workflow management system [ewoks](#) automates data processing and experiments at large-scale facilities and makes them more scientific (reproducible) and FAIR (traceable).
- [Mantid](#) is a framework for HPC and visualisation of neutron scattering data.
- [PyMca](#) collection of Python tools to assist on common data analysis problems.
- [ParSeq](#) is a general analysis framework based on a python software library for Parallel execution of Sequential data analysis.

4.1.7. Future Perspectives

For the future perspective of the PaNOSC portfolio, different options are currently under discussion. We think that the extensive catalogue should be available in PaNOSC to search for desired tools following the idea of a marketplaces from different institutions. Currently, PaNOSC is a EOSC candidate node and could become one of the first EOSC thematic nodes and thus could shape the future collaborations within the EOSC Federation. As such a thematic node, PaNOSC could host its own marketplace, following the example of the SSH Open Marketplace, for which SSHOC already shared the source code with the PaN community and, thus, paved the way for quick and simple start.

Independently of the previous options, the collected software might be integrated in the [PaNdata Software Catalogue](#).

4.2. SSHOC Portfolio

The consolidation of the SSHOC Cluster portfolio is one of the dimensions discussed by the Cluster Governing Board as part of its strategy and SSHOC priorities for 2024–2028.

The SSH Open Marketplace, as one of the Cluster services, is currently acting as a curated discovery portal of SSH resources for the Cluster community and being funded and maintained by three ERICs. As part of the portfolio consolidation efforts conducted in OSCARS, all SSH resources from the [EOSC data dump](#) were identified and added to the SSH Open Marketplace in order to provide a comprehensive and large overview of the SSH resources available via the EOSC onboarding (between 2029 and 2024). This list of 66 services is available at the [SSH Open Marketplace](#).

To increase the interoperability of the imported EOSC services with existing entries in the SSH Open Marketplace, it was necessary to create mappings between properties used in the

EOSC data dump and vocabularies used in the SSH Open Marketplace. For example, the field *Scientific Domain* and *Scientific Subdomain* had to be manually mapped to the Austrian Fields of Science and Technology Classification ([ÖFOS 2012](#)). Where both EOSC and SSH Open Marketplace used freetext properties, these properties could be carried over. As the import of the EOSC data dump was performed using the ingest library in a Jupyter Notebook, every step of data processing is transparent and documented.

Further curation and maintenance of this catalogue could be envisioned as one of the tasks coordinated by the SSH Open Marketplace Editorial Board, in which a large part of the Cluster community is already represented.

In addition to these efforts of gathering resources to consolidate the SSHOC service offer, it should also be noted that other ongoing EU-projects are contributing to a better alignment of the SSHOC (data) catalogues and aggregators. SSHOC pilots in [OSTrails](#) or the SSH vocabularies alignment efforts conducted in the [ATRIUM project](#) (and involving the ARIADNE portal, the CLARIN Virtual Language Observatory, the GoTriple platform from OPERAS and the SSH Open Marketplace) are direct contributions to a more coherent and interoperable catalogues landscape for the SSHOC Cluster.

4.3. ENVRI Portfolio

The [ENVRI-Hub](#) serves as a comprehensive gateway for environmental and Earth science RIs, offering a suite of advanced services designed to facilitate data access, analysis, training, and collaboration across diverse scientific disciplines. Below is a detailed description of the service portfolio provided by ENVRI-Hub:

Figure 2 – Visualisation of the service portfolio provided by ENVRI-Hub

4.3.1. Catalogues of Data and Services

ENVRI-Hub hosts an extensive set of catalogues, enabling users to discover and access a wide range of services and datasets from participating research infrastructures. These include:

- [ENVRI Service Catalogue](#)

A centralized repository of individual services provided by RIs in the environmental sciences domain. Users can explore and leverage tools tailored to their specific research needs.

- **RI-Specific Catalogues**

The hub aggregates data and services from specific RIs, including:

- a. **eLTER Catalogue:** Long-term ecosystem research.
- b. **EPOS Catalogue:** Earth science data and services.
- c. **LifeWatch Catalogue:** Biodiversity and ecosystem data.
- d. **SeaDataNet Catalogue:** Oceanographic data.
- e. **EuroArgo Catalogue:** Ocean monitoring resources.
- f. **ICOS Catalogue:** Carbon observation data.

These catalogues provide a unified interface for discovering domain-specific datasets and services.

4.3.2. Training Catalogue

The [ENVRI-Hub Training Catalogue](#) offers a curated collection of educational resources and training materials aimed at enhancing researchers' capabilities in data management, analysis, and advanced technologies. Key features include:

- Interactive courses on FAIR data principles and management.
- Workshops on advanced tools and methodologies for environmental research.
- Access to recorded webinars and step-by-step guides.

4.3.3. Knowledge Base and Search Engine

To streamline information discovery, ENVRI-Hub integrates a powerful [search engine](#) connected to its Knowledge Base. This tool provides:

- **Comprehensive Search Capabilities:** Allows users to query datasets, services, and educational resources.
- **Metadata Integration:** Facilitates detailed exploration through rich metadata for better data discovery and understanding.

4.3.4. Virtual Research Environment (VRE)

The [Notebook-as-a-Virtual-Research-Environment \(NaaVRE\)](#) offers an interactive platform for conducting sophisticated research workflows. Features include:

- **Research Software Integration:** Access to pre-configured tools and software for data analysis and visualization.
- **Virtual Labs:** Enable researchers to execute end-to-end workflows for climate modeling, biodiversity monitoring, and more.
- **Customizable Notebooks:** Support for Jupyter notebooks that allow users to integrate code, data, and narrative in a seamless manner.
- **Examples of VRE Use Cases:**
 - Automated quality checks for scientific software.
 - Interactive workflows for analyzing essential climate variables.

4.3.5. Quality Guidelines and Tools

ENVRI-Hub emphasizes the importance of maintaining high standards for software and data quality. It provides:

- **Quality-Aware Discovery Tools:** Allow researchers to identify software assets that meet specific quality criteria.
- **Automated Quality Checks:** Tools for programmers to validate and improve the quality of their code and data workflows.
- **Guidelines for Scientific Programmers:** Best practices to ensure reproducibility and efficiency in software development.

4.3.6. Advanced Analytics Framework

ENVRI-Hub supports a framework for integrating and analyzing large datasets, enabling:

- Multi-domain data analysis with scalable computational resources.
- Harmonization of datasets across different RIs for interdisciplinary research.
- Custom workflows to address complex environmental challenges.

Summary

The **ENVRI-Hub Service Portfolio** offers an integrated suite of tools designed to enhance data discovery, usability, and interoperability in environmental sciences. From comprehensive catalogues, analytics framework and training resources to virtual research environments and quality assurance tools, ENVRI-Hub supports researchers in advancing interdisciplinary science and fostering collaboration across diverse domains.

Path Forward

The ENVRI-Hub portfolio will continue to evolve as a "living document," reflecting updates in resources and user needs. The focus will remain on enhancing composability, fostering knowledge exchange, and ensuring seamless integration with EOSC to maximise the impact of environmental research infrastructures.

This starting point establishes ENVRI as a well-prepared Cluster with significant potential to advance interoperability, open science practices, and interdisciplinary research under the OSCARS project framework.

4.4. LS-RI Portfolio

The LS-RI community portfolio is constantly evolving, as the need to structure the services of the involved communities is continuously enriched with new solutions to emerging needs linked to complex disciplines, which are fully interconnected and rely on increasingly interoperable data describing their contexts ([David et al, 2022](#)). Integrated approaches require collaborations among all RIs developing their services and are working on minimum requirements and metadata standards. Packaging Metadata with data and their related workflows ([Goble, et al, 2020](#)), software, and environments becomes a priority for most data producers and a condition sine qua non for data reusers to avoid misuse of shared data and increase the power of necessary meta-analyses.

4.4.1. Unifying data description

- Minimum metadata schema + metadata governance
 - [Bioschemas](#): Community-defined metadata specifications for life sciences resources
 - [FAIRtracks](#): A set of JSON Schemas defining a draft minimal standard used to consolidate genomic track metadata from various sources, which can be queried by downstream clients.
- Data identification / traceability / protection
 - [ELIXIR AAI \(Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure\)](#) for data protection and secure access.
 - [Identifiers.org](#): Persistent and unique identifiers for datasets.
 - [Sensitive data tagging in life science research](#): Toolbox described in a paper: "An iterative and interdisciplinary categorisation process towards FAIRer digital resources for sensitive life-sciences data" ([David et al, 2022](#))
- Provenance metadata standardisation efforts
- Umbrella data management tools / DMPs /

- [Data Stewardship Wizard \(DSW\)](#): Tool for creating Data Management Plans (DMPs).
- [FAIRDOM-SEEK](#): Platform supporting data and model management under FAIR principles.
- [MOLGENIS](#): Flexible data integration platform to facilitate FAIR research data and accelerate scientific collaborations.

4.4.2. Decentralised and interoperable catalogues of Data and Services

- [FAIRsharing](#) as a registry for standards, databases, policies and related objects. Supports DOI minting for items in the registry.
- [RO-Crate](#) as a data metadata-enriched packaging for workflows and datasets that facilitates reuse and reproducibility. Interoperable with FAIR tools like FAIRDOM-SEEK and WorkflowHub.
- [WorkflowHub](#) as a catalog to facilitate discovery and re-use of workflows in an accessible and interoperable way. Extensive use of open standards and tools, including RO-Crate, Bioschemas and GA4GH's TRS API. Supports all workflow languages, including Common Workflow Language, Galaxy, KNIME, Nextflow, Snakemake
- Thematic and specialised repositories / Data mobilisation processes
 - BBMRI: [BBMRI-ERIC: Sample and Data Portal](#) - biobanks
 - ELIXIR: [ELIXIR Core Data Resources](#) (e.g. [European Nucleotide Archive](#)) and [BioImage Archive](#).
 - EU-OPENSREEN: [EU-OPENSREEN: Compound Collections](#) for Chemical Biology and Drug Discovery
 - INFRAFRONTIER-ERIC: European Mutant Mouse Archive [EMMA](#)
 - MIRRI-ERIC: Catalogue of [Microbial Resources & Data](#)
 - EMBL: [EMBL-EBI data repositories](#) (e.g. BioImage Archive, EMPIAR,..)
 - Euro-BioImaging: [data services](#)
- Sensitive data access
 - [Beacon Network](#) for discovery of genomic data under controlled access.
 - [Federated European Genome-phenome Archive](#) (FEGA) for permanent archiving and sharing of personally identifiable genetic, phenotypic, and clinical data generated for the purposes of biomedical research projects or in the context of research-focused healthcare systems
 - Unified LS Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI) services: [Life Science AAI](#)
- Open science, Zotero and Zenodo related community pages

4.4.3. Interoperate Data and other digital objects

- Data curation / Data aggregation / Data contextualisation

- [ELIXIR Core Data Resources](#) for curated and high-quality datasets.
- [BioSamples](#) stores and supplies descriptions and metadata about biological samples used in research and development by academia and industry enabling multi-omics analysis.
- SSSM and crosswalk repositories
- Software interoperability and sustainability
 - [bio.tools](#): registry of software tools and data resources for life sciences.
 - [BioContainers](#): list of software that can run on any operating system.
 - [OpenEBench](#): tools for benchmarking and monitoring software.
 - [Workflowhub.eu](#): registry for describing, sharing and publishing scientific computational workflows.

4.4.4. Data Analysis services for better reproducibility

- Virtual Research environments
 - [Galaxy Project](#) - UseGalaxy.eu: accessible analysis of data with more than 2500 tools, visualisations and 200 reference genomes.
- Artificial intelligence
 - [DOME](#) Registry for FAIR ML/AI model deposition
- Other services for data /DO reuse
Note this part must be consolidated in the near future.

4.4.5. Training and support tools usable for FAIR literacy

- Training and workshop programmes and infrastructures
 - EATRIS: [Transmed Academy – EATRIS](#) for translational medicine
 - EBI: [Competency Hub](#) competencies, career profiles and training resources for LS
 - ECRIN: [Training | Ecrin](#) for clinical trials
 - ELIXIR: [ELIXIR Training Portal \(TeSS\)](#) for centralized training resources.
 - EMBL: [Training at EMBL](#) for molecular biology
 - EMBRC: [MarineTraining](#) for marine training
 - EMPHASIS: [Training Pilot - Emphasis](#) for plant phenotyping
 - ERINHA: [Training - ERINHA](#) for biosafety and biosecurity
 - EU-OPENSREEN: [EU-OPENSREEN: Training](#) for Chemical Biology & Medicine Chemistry
 - Euro-Biolmaging: [Training - Euro-Biolmaging](#) for biological and biomedical imaging
 - EVAg: [European Virus Archive](#) for virology compounds database
 - INFRAFRONTIER: [Services - INFRAFRONTIER](#) FAIR data resource for disease models
 - INSTRUCT: [Instruct Training Events](#) for structural biology

- MIRRI: [Find Courses – MIRRI-ERIC](#) for microbial resources
- LifeWatch: <https://trainingcatalogue.lifewatch.eu/home/> for biodiversity and ecosystems
- Guidelines and recommendations
 - [RDMkit \(Research Data Management kit\)](#): A guide to best practices for managing research data.
 - [FAIR Cookbook](#): A live, open, online, collaborative resource of hands-on recipes for “FAIR doers” in the Life Sciences.
 - EOSC components, such as [EOSC Task Forces](#) and [EOSC Opportunity Area expert groups](#)
- Support and incentives for good practices dissemination
 - [Be Sustainable Model](#) (EOSC-Life output)
 - EOSC Platform: [EOSC EU Node](#)

Summary

The LS-RI Service Portfolio presents a suite of services and tools, some shared and others interconnected across RIs, aimed at continuously improving interoperability as well as harmonised, traceable, protectable, and adaptable processes and standards. Initiatives such as Bioschemas, FAIRtracks and platforms such as MOLGENIS are examples of how to facilitate seamless data sharing and re-use across the life sciences community. These developments can be important in addressing complex disciplinary needs and fostering collaboration between research infrastructures.

4.5. ESCAPE Portfolio

The current content of the ESCAPE portfolio addresses the essential elements needed to perform a standard physics workflow, including data production and lifecycle, data analysis, results publication and citizen science activities. While rooted in high-energy physics, astronomy, and astrophysics, these pillars are designed with flexibility and composability, making them applicable across a wide range of scientific domains.

4.5.1. Distributed Data Management

- [Rucio](#): A modular platform addressing large-scale data management, integrating diverse storage systems and globally distributed data centers.
- **File Transfer System (FTS)**: Ensures reliable bulk transfers of data across the computing infrastructure.
- **Content Delivery and Latency Hiding mechanisms**: software-managed disk storage caching layers that enhance file reusability and hide latency, allowing efficient CPU use by streaming data from the local cache.

- **Hierarchical Progressive Survey (HiPS)**: standard for the description, storage and access of large sky survey data across multiple international nodes.

4.5.2. Data Analysis and Reproducibility

- **REANA**: A reusable platform for structuring and executing research workflows on remote compute clouds.

4.5.3. Open Science and Repositories

- **Zenodo**: An open-access repository for sharing and preserving research outputs in any format or size.
- **Open-Source Scientific Software Repository (OSSR)**: Sustainable open-access repository to share scientific software, services and datasets to the astro-particle-physics-related communities via FAIR compliant metadata schemas.

4.5.4. Outreach and collaborative initiatives

- **European Virtual Observatory (EURO-VO)**: Enables global electronic access to astronomical data archives and surveys.
- **Citizen Science**: Enables the public to conduct research while promoting ESCAPE services and FAIR principles.
- **International Virtual Observatory Alliance (IVOA)**: Interoperability standards for astronomical data through collaborative efforts.

These services, although they can be used independently, can also be unified through the **VRE**, whose highly composability enables end-to-end physics workflows. The VRE acts as a central hub, allowing users to interface with the various ESCAPE services within a single platform, thanks to the ESCAPE Identity and Access Management (IAM) service.

Many research infrastructures utilise or maintain one or more of these services, fostering their continuous improvement, ongoing support, and the steady growth of their community.

5. Initial Exploration of Composability Scenarios

As [outlined](#) by the European Commission, the ambition of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is to provide European researchers with a federated and open multi-disciplinary environment where they can publish, find, and reuse data, tools, and services for research, innovation and educational purposes. A crucial part of this work is to ensure that EOSC provides value for the research communities that it intends to serve. The Science Clusters and their constituent research infrastructures are best placed to ensure this happens.

It is therefore essential that the work undertaken in OSCARS WP2 responds to the needs of the researchers who will discover, use and in the future compose the services and data sources identified by the Science Clusters for their day-to-day work. This will enable EOSC to become a **researcher-focused infrastructure**. As part of this work, better understanding of the needs of these research communities is needed.

As a first step in this researcher-focused approach, an initial list of considerations or a ‘**researcher value proposition**’, has been provided:

Research Focus and Expertise

- Highlight any unique methodologies, technologies, or approaches that differentiate the research.

Impact and Relevance

- significance of the research, potential impact on society, industry, academia
- current trends, challenges, or needs in the field.

Expected Outcomes and Benefits (for stakeholders)

- tangible benefits, e.g. advancements in knowledge, technological innovations, or solutions to pressing problems.

Collaboration and Partnerships, Interdisciplinarity

- collaboration with other researchers, institutions, or industry partners.

Track Record and Credentials

- past successes, such as publications, grants, awards, or successful projects.
- any relevant qualifications, experience, or recognition that establish credibility

Funding and Resource Needs

- Explain how the investment will lead to significant returns or advancements in the field.

Communication and Dissemination (to stakeholders and broader community)

- plans for publications, presentations, or outreach activities to ensure visibility and impact.

Long-term Vision

- future projects, innovations, or developments in the field.

Addressing Challenges and Barriers, Taking Precautions

Finally, as exemplified through the [OSCARS Open Calls](#), the role of the Science Clusters, is to issue a **call to action**, inviting stakeholders to engage, collaborate, or support the research.

For EOSC to reach its full potential, the possibility of interconnecting FAIR Data Sources, Tools, Services and Software as well as Research Outputs, including publications, datasets and code, into Reproducible Research Workflows, based on Open Science practices is crucial. This interconnection process, within the context of EOSC and OSCARS, is known as *composability*.

The following sections include some typical research scenarios within the different Science Clusters, including established workflows, services, and data sources. These scenarios do not only highlight the status quo, but also future potential that can be exploited when making certain services composable in the next step of the project. During the Consolidation Workshop, the participants decided to follow the common baseline of the scenarios to include the input, processing, and output of research data.

5.1. PaNOSC Scenarios

Within the PaN community, the research data generally analyzes the interaction of the neutron or synchrotron beam with a sample. This interaction can be characterized by changing different parameters, e.g. position of the sample relative to the beam, the beam energy, the *in-situ* conditions of the sample. Data treatment is an essential point in nearly every scientific scenario and strongly depends

Figure 3 – Experiment at a synchrotron, ©2025 Deutsches Elektronen-Synchrotron DESY

on the chosen method, especially differentiating between the underlying probes (e.g. x-rays, neutrons), but also the physical process (e.g. absorption, diffraction).

We will not only outline the individual steps of the various scenarios but also recommend appropriate services or software to implement them. The chosen resources from the portfolio are marked in bold.

5.1.1. PaNOSC Scenario 1: Data Download via DOI

1. **Data Search** using the [European Photon and Neutron Open Data Search Portal](#) (further development within [OSCARS Open Call Projects](#) (OOPC) [PaN-Finder](#)); possible search options: technique, facility, formula, incident wavelength or energy, temperature, pressure; forwarding to different data storages, e.g. [SciCat](#) and [iCat](#); possible improvements: define and connect all PaN data repositories to a PaN Data Commons (this might also involve the databases under development within the OOPC *AMBCAT*, *OpenCorrAM*, *SHARE*, *MatScatNet*, *ioChem-BD*).
2. **(Raw) Data Download**: manual download of referenced data. Possible improvement: automated and unified download on the basis of the doi (potentially cross-cluster), using a metadata querying interface based on content negotiation of HTTP with focus on FAIR data (no authentication required) and RI collaborations; consisting of triggering stage, error handling, defining the metalink profile, and transferring data based on different download options (available via IRI), e.g. HTTP, Globus, RSync, OneData, IRODS, Rucio
3. **Data Treatment**, including several individual steps, depending on the underlying technique (which should be listed in the metadata of the dataset in a standardized way, e.g. using the [PaNET](#) ontology; upcoming improvements within OOPC [Findable Big Data from Various Material Characterisation Techniques](#)):
 - Training on data treatment and other topics available at [PaN Training](#), upcoming improvements within OOPC [mTeSS-X](#)
 - example with services for small angle x-ray scattering at ESRF using [VISA](#) (further improvement with OOPC [VISA: User experience enhancement](#)):
 - a. **Corrections**, e.g. [BornAgain](#), [pyFAI](#), [ATSAS](#)
 - b. **Analysis**, e.g. [BornAgain](#), [pyNX](#), [ATSAS](#)
 - c. **Visualization**, e.g. [H5Web](#) (cross-cluster format, possible improvements: support files of unlimited size), [BornAgain](#), [pyMca](#)
 - d. **Simulation**, e.g. [ATSAS](#)
4. **Storage of Refined Data**, upload by scientist to original RI or other data portal: e.g. [iCAT](#) and [SciCat](#), [DESY library](#), [ESRF Data Portal](#)
5. **Collaborative Text Editing**, e.g. [Overleaf @ HZDR](#), [SciFlow @ HZB](#), [XeLaTeX @ ESRF](#)
6. **Publishing**, e.g. [Episciences](#), [ResearchGate](#), [B2SHARE @ FZJ](#)
7. **Publication Storage**, e.g. [RoBIS @ HZDR](#), [Zenodo](#), [ePubs @ STFC](#), [Scopus](#), [RES3T @ HZDR](#)
8. Present results at **conferences (organized and published with [indico](#))**
9. Further development in OOPC [MatScatNet](#) (industry contribution) and [AI-SCOPE](#)

5.1.2. PaNOSC Scenario 2: Way for Light and PaNET

1. Aiming to reproduce the results of an interesting publication
2. **Finding European beamlines** that are capable of reproducing the data using [Way For Light](#) (WFL), [RIANA](#), [ReMade@ARI](#); possible search options in WFL: technique (e.g. absorption, diffraction), facility (within Europe), discipline (e.g. chemistry, life sciences), sample type (e.g. crystal, amorphous), beam polarization, beam energy; possible improvements:
 - Cross-link to PaNET, more detailed and exact information
 - Extend WFL for information on sample environments
 - Create/improve API for WFL
3. **Write and submit beamtime proposal** using the RI's upload page, login with AAI, e.g. [umbrellaID](#), [EOSC AAI](#), EOSC ID; or using a single-entry-point providing overarching project, e.g. [RIANA](#), [ReMade@ARI](#)
4. Beamtime gets approved and scheduled
5. Prepare samples and equipment
6. Conduct beamtime
 - **Remote beamtime secured via AAI**
 - **Online analysis**, e.g. [ASAP::O @ DESY](#)
 - **Electronic lab notebooks (ELN)**, e.g. [eLabFTW](#), [Chemotion ELN](#), [Labfolder](#)
 - (Online) safety training
 - **Beamline control**, e.g. [Sardana](#), [BlueSky](#), [BLISS](#)
 - **Experimental control**, e.g. [SECoP](#), [Tango](#), [EPICS](#)
7. **Store raw data**, preferably in [NeXus](#) format (related to HDF5), including metadata (ongoing discussions on required/mandatory information, also within the OOPC [MC-ReDD](#) and [CODEMETASOFT](#)), e.g. SciCat, iCAT
8. **Transfer data** to preferred VRE (e.g. company's server or VISA at home institute), transfer e.g. via [EOSC Data Transfer Service](#), [Globus Connect Personal](#), [Rucio](#) (potential cross-cluster service, with ESCAPE); possible improvements:
 - Explore synergies with other Clusters and the EOSC EU Node to adopt and share standards for Data Transfer.
 - Improve the process to get a login.
 - Explore synergy with other Clusters to adopt and share standards for VREs.
9. **Data Treatment**, see Scenario 1, step 3; example for x-ray absorption spectroscopy:
 - **Corrections**, e.g. [Hephaestus](#), [ParSeq](#)
 - **Analysis**, e.g. [Athena](#), [Artemis](#), [IFEFFIT](#), ParSeq
 - **Visualization**, e.g. H5Web, pyMca, ParSeq

- **Simulation**, e.g. [FDMNES](#)
- The experimental data is often compared to a reference or previous experiments, stored in databases (metadata standards are under development within the OOPC [CDIF-4-XAS](#)), e.g. [X-Ray Absorption Spectroscopy Library](#), [Actinide Reference Database for Spectroscopy](#), [X-Ray Absorption Spectroscopy database](#)

10. Collaboratively produce a paper, publish it, and store the publication (steps 4 – 8 from Scenario 1) further developments in OOPC [CDIF-4-XAS](#)

5.2. SSHOC Scenarios

The [SSH Open Marketplace](#) is an essential resource for researchers in the Social Sciences and Humanities, offering tools, datasets, and workflows that support diverse research processes. Below are two proposed workflows designed to enhance research capabilities using resources from the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). These workflows address the specific needs of digitised historical newspaper research and oral history interview analysis and anonymisation. In both use cases, the main focus is on resource interoperability. An initial visualisation of a generic Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) workflow is provided in Figure 4 below:

Figure 4 – An initial visualisation of a generic SSH workflow which could be used for multiple research scenarios

5.2.1. SSHOC Scenario 1: digitised historical newspapers

Objective:

To create an efficient workflow for processing, analysing, and visualising digitised historical newspapers. This scenario will assist researchers in handling large corpora of historical texts, focusing on tasks such as text digitisation, Optical Character Recognition (OCR) improvement, metadata extraction, and historical linguistic analysis.

Workflow Steps:

1. Data Collection:

- Identify relevant newspaper archives (e.g. [120 currently in SSHOMP](#), provided by CLARIN Resource Families)
- Select the specific digitised newspaper datasets (e.g. [British Library's News Datasets](#)) to be used.

2. OCR and Text Enhancement:

- Utilise tools such as [Transkribus](#) or [Tesseract OCR](#) for OCR processing and quality improvement.
- Integrate post-OCR correction tools to enhance text readability and accuracy.

3. Metadata Enrichment and Annotation:

- Enrich metadata using linked open data resources such as [WikiData](#).
- Annotate text content with semantic tagging tools to support historical research (e.g., [Named Entity Recognition](#) for people, places, and dates).

4. Text Mining and Analysis:

- Apply natural language processing (NLP) workflows for keyword extraction, [sentiment analysis](#), and [topic modeling](#) using SSH Marketplace - listed tools like **Voyant Tools** or **AntConc**.
- Visualize trends and insights through interactive dashboards for comparative research across time periods and regions.

5. Collaboration and Sharing:

- Store and [share](#) enriched datasets and results on open platforms, ensuring compliance with FAIR data principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).

Potential SSHOMP Resources:

- [Europeana Newspaper Collections](#)
- [CLARIN Resources Families](#)
- Zenodo for dataset sharing

Consideration for Different Digital Literacy Levels:

The narrative approach in this workflow provides clear step-by-step guidance and

recommended tools for each task, making it accessible to researchers with varying levels of digital literacy.

- **Beginner-Level Users:** Benefit from descriptive tool explanations, tutorials, and basic NLP workflows with visual interfaces (e.g., Voyant Tools).
- **Intermediate-Level Users:** Can customise OCR correction workflows and conduct more detailed metadata annotations.
- **Advanced Users:** Gain flexibility to build complex text mining pipelines, integrate Python scripts, and contribute enhancements to open-source tools.

5.2.2. SSHOC Scenario 2: oral history interviews

Objective:

To develop a robust workflow for managing, analyzing, and anonymizing oral history interview data. This scenario supports researchers in processing audio-visual interviews, generating transcriptions, and anonymizing sensitive information to comply with ethical and legal standards.

Workflow Steps:

1. **Data Collection and Import:**
 - Collect and upload audio and video files of oral history interviews provided, for example, through [CESSDA Data Catalogue](#).
 - Import previously recorded transcriptions, where available, into the workflow.
2. **Transcription and Alignment:**
 - Use transcription tools such as [ELAN](#), **Speech-to-Text APIs (e.g., [Whisper](#))**, or [CLARIN Speech Services](#) for automatic transcription and speaker alignment.
3. **Anonymisation of Personal Data:**
 - Apply [anonymisation](#) frameworks to detect and remove personally identifiable information (PII).
 - Use tools such as [BAS Web Services](#) for automated anonymization of sensitive text segments.
4. **Qualitative Analysis:**
 - Perform qualitative analysis using tools such as [ATLAS.ti](#) or [Nvivo](#) for coding and thematic exploration.
 - Generate reports on emerging themes, narratives, and patterns in interview data.
5. **Preservation and Sharing:**
 - Store anonymized transcripts and analysis outputs in secure repositories.
 - Ensure compliance with General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) for long-term preservation and access.

Potential SSHOMP Resources:

- SSHOC Training Modules on Data Management and Anonymisation
- CLARIN Tools for Speech and Language Processing
- Zenodo for long-term archival of anonymized interview transcripts

Consideration for Different Digital Literacy Levels:

This narrative workflow addresses the diverse needs of SSH researchers by offering adaptable paths based on technical expertise. These paths can be realized by referring researchers to different steps in one workflow, or by presenting three separate workflows.

- **Beginner-Level Users:** Access ready-to-use transcription tools with minimal setup and follow step-by-step anonymisation templates.
- **Intermediate-Level Users:** Experiment with customized coding schemes for qualitative analysis and integrate semi-automated workflows.
- **Advanced Users:** Leverage APIs for fine-grained speech-to-text processing and contribute anonymization scripts to collaborative repositories.

Cross-Cluster Considerations

Both scenarios aim to leverage resources available in the EOSC EU Node for data collection, processing, and sharing. The workflows can be further enhanced by adopting cross-cluster collaborations, allowing researchers from different SSH domains to share best practices, tools, and insights via the SSH Open Marketplace.

5.3. ENVRI Scenarios

5.3.1. ENVRI Scenario 1: Integrated Climate Data Analysis Using the ENVRI-Hub VRE

A researcher is studying the impacts of climate change, e.g., Essential Climate Variables (ECV) and on oceanic carbon uptake, and needs to analyze large datasets from multiple sources, including oceanographic observations, atmospheric CO₂ measurements, and satellite imagery. The researcher requires tools for data discovery, integration, workflow management and advanced analysis.

Steps:

1. Data and Service Discovery:

- The researcher accesses the **ENVRI Service Catalogue** and searches for datasets from specific infrastructures such as:
 - **EuroArgo Catalogue:** Provides oceanographic float data, including salinity, temperature, and carbon fluxes.

- **ICOS Catalogue:** Supplies atmospheric CO₂ measurements from observation stations.
 - **SeaDataNet Catalogue:** Offers historical datasets on ocean conditions.
 - Using the integrated **Knowledge Base Search Engine**, the researcher refines searches based on metadata to locate datasets relevant to oceanic carbon dynamics.
- 2. Data Integration:**
- The researcher downloads datasets in standardized formats, ensuring interoperability across sources.
 - Using the **Notebook-as-a-Virtual-Research-Environment (NaaVRE)**, the researcher imports data into a Jupyter notebook, enabling integration and visualization.
- 3. Data Analysis:**
- The researcher employs tools within the VRE to:
 - Analyze oceanic carbon uptake trends.
 - Compare atmospheric CO₂ levels with oceanographic data.
 - Model interactions between atmospheric and oceanic systems using predefined workflows.
- 4. Collaboration and Sharing:**
- The analysis results, including visualizations and processed datasets, are uploaded back to the VRE for collaborative review.
 - Persistent identifiers (DOIs) are assigned to ensure proper citation and compliance with FAIR principles.

Outcome:

The researcher gains valuable insights into climate-ocean interactions, publishes reproducible workflows, and shares findings with collaborators through ENVRI-Hub, fostering interdisciplinary research.

5.3.2. ENVRI Scenario 2: Biodiversity Monitoring and Ecosystem Health Assessment

A team of ecologists is investigating biodiversity loss in a protected forest area. They aim to integrate field observations, remote sensing data, and climate variables to assess ecosystem health and propose conservation strategies.

Steps:

1. Training and Competence Building:

- The team accesses the **ENVRI Training Catalogue** to participate in a workshop on using remote sensing tools and FAIR data management.

- They gain expertise in leveraging ENVRI-Hub services for ecosystem monitoring.

2. Data Collection and Discovery:

- Field observations, such as species counts and habitat conditions, are uploaded to the ENVRI-Hub Knowledge Base.
- The team discovers complementary datasets from:
 - **LifeWatch Catalogue:** Provides species distribution data and ecological models.
 - **EPOS Catalogue:** Offers geospatial data on soil conditions and seismic activity.
 - **eLTER Catalogue:** Supplies long-term environmental monitoring data from the region.

3. Data Analysis:

- The team uses the VRE to:
 - Overlay biodiversity data with remote sensing imagery and climate variables.
 - Analyze habitat fragmentation and changes in ecosystem services.
 - Apply machine learning algorithms to identify trends in species distribution.

4. Quality Assurance:

- Automated quality checks are performed on the integrated datasets to ensure reliability and reproducibility.
- The team uses ENVRI-Hub's guidelines for software and data quality to refine their workflows.

5. Reporting and Advocacy:

- Findings are compiled into a report with interactive visualizations generated using VRE tools.
- The results are shared with policymakers and conservation organizations via ENVRI-Hub's community platform, supporting evidence-based decision-making.

Outcome:

The team produces actionable insights into biodiversity loss and ecosystem health, contributing to conservation strategies and fulfilling obligations for open data sharing under FAIR principles.

5.4. LS-RI Scenarios

CC Implementation Scenarios in LS-RIs

We describe the **design, implementation, and integration of Competence Centres (CCs)** within the LS-RI Cluster in a community paper ([David et al., 2025 - manuscript in preparation](#)). We focused on:

- collating **community-based ideas and recommendations** to leverage CCs to address sustainability, governance, scalability, interoperability, and Open Science challenges within EOSC and the European Research Area (ERA), and
- building **scenarios for implementing the CC concept** into the LS-RI Cluster.

In the LS-RI Cluster, the community agreed that CCs can act as dynamic hubs to “foster innovation, contribute to the EOSC FAIR web of data, and support future development of the EOSC Federation”. For the establishment of CCs in the LS-RI Cluster, it is necessary to consider how CCs can be set up and operated to optimise support for researchers. Two key implementation scenarios have been iteratively developed through an LS-RI community-driven process in the community paper and are reproduced below ([David et al., 2025 - manuscript in preparation](#)).

Scenario 1: Federated CC Network

The first scenario, closer to the current state of the LS-RI Cluster community, accommodates for the diverse, existing services within various LS communities and RIs, allowing for greater flexibility and tailored approaches. This scenario envisions a network of federated CCs, each embedded within individual LS-RIs but connected through a shared framework for collaboration and interoperability, as depicted in Figure 5 below.

Scenario 1: Federated Competence Centre Network

This scenario envisions a network of federated CCs, each embedded within individual LS-RIs but connected through a shared framework for collaboration and interoperability.

Figure 5 – Implementation Scenario 1 for CCs in LS-RIs - Federated Competence Centre Network.

The first scenario follows key implementation steps identified by a collective of LS-RI community representatives - version in validation step ([David et al., 2025](#)), addressing challenges and benefits associated with governance, funding, interoperability, and sustainability:

- **Implementation Steps:**
 - **Awareness and Community Engagement:** Foster engagement through targeted outreach, emphasizing the benefits of a federated approach.
 - **Funding and Policy Alignment:** Secure funding for individual CCs while aligning them with overarching EOSC policies.
 - **Incentives for FAIR Practices:** Encourage FAIR data practices through reward systems and recognition within each CC.
 - **Skills Development and Harmonisation:** Organise cross-RI workshops to harmonise skills and knowledge sharing.

- **Storage and Infrastructure:** Establish federated cloud infrastructures that allow for local autonomy while ensuring interoperability.
- **Benefits:**
 - Flexibility for LS-RIs to tailor CCs to their specific needs.
 - Enhanced collaboration across institutions while preserving local strengths.
 - Scalable model adaptable to different disciplines and regions.
- **Challenges:**
 - Ensuring consistent quality and interoperability across diverse CCs.
 - More complex coordination and governance structures.

Example 1: Federated CC Network Enabling Federated Data Access for Sensitive Research

Scientific research increasingly relies on **sensitive datasets**, such as **genomic, clinical, and socio-economic data**, which require strict security and access control. The Horizon Europe funded [EOSC-ENTRUST](#) project, coordinated by [ELIXIR](#), is aimed at **creating a federated network of Trusted Research Environments (TREs)** to facilitate secure data access while ensuring compliance with legal and ethical guidelines.

One of EOSC-ENTRUST's key applications is in **genomic medicine**. Traditionally, patient genomic data is stored in isolated, institution-specific databases, limiting researchers' ability to conduct **multi-center studies**. By **federating access to these datasets**, EOSC-ENTRUST allows scientists to perform **privacy-preserving analysis** on sensitive data across multiple institutions without needing to transfer raw data.

A specific example is its application in **cancer research**. Using federated analysis tools, researchers across Europe can **access encrypted genomic datasets, run AI-driven algorithms**, and derive insights on cancer progression **without compromising patient confidentiality**. This approach not only accelerates **drug discovery** but also ensures that sensitive patient data remains protected under GDPR-compliant standards.

Additionally, EOSC-ENTRUST is addressing challenges in **social science and public health research**. For example, socio-economic data related to **mental health, employment, and healthcare accessibility** can now be analysed in a **secure, federated manner**, enabling researchers to **correlate public policy impacts with health outcomes**.

By implementing **shared technical, legal, and governance frameworks**, EOSC-ENTRUST is therefore setting a **new standard for secure research collaboration** across disciplines, ensuring that sensitive data can be leveraged for scientific discoveries **without compromising privacy**.

Scenario 2: LS-RI Cluster-based CC Model

The Cluster-based CC scenario envisions a centralised CC serving multiple LS-RIs under a unified governance and operational framework as depicted in Figure 6, below.

Scenario 2: LS-RI Cluster-based Competence Centre Model

In this scenario, a main hub for Competence Centre (CC) is established to serve multiple LS-RIs under a unified governance and operational framework.

Figure 6: Implementation Scenario for CCs in LS-RIs - LS-RI Cluster-based CC Model.

The second scenario also follows key implementation steps identified in the LS-RI community paper on CCs along with challenges and benefits (David et al., 2025):

- **Implementation Steps:**
 - **Definition and Consensus:** Launch participatory across LS-RIs to define the CCs scope and mission.
 - **Governance Simplification:** Develop a streamlined governance model with clear roles and responsibilities, avoiding administrative redundancies.
 - **Interoperability and Standardisation:** Implement harmonised tools and software standards to ensure seamless data integration.
 - **Data Stewardship and Quality Control:** Create a central registry for data stewards, promoting consistent data quality practices.
 - **Sustainability and Funding:** Secure continuous funding through European Commission grants and integrate EOSC recommendations.
- **Benefits:**
 - Uniform standards and practices across LS-RIs.
 - Centralised training and resource allocation, ensuring cost-efficiency.
 - Simplified policy alignment and governance.

- **Challenges:**
 - Coordination and resourcing of Hub.
 - Potential resistance from LS-RIs preferring autonomy.
 - High initial investment for centralised infrastructure.

This second scenario offers a solution for shared missions, skills, and resources common to most LS-RIs. A centralised CC could act as the "hub" of LS CCs, providing a unified framework to streamline efforts across the research landscape.

In practice, the most effective approach will likely combine elements from both models. A **centralised "hub" of LS CCs** could manage shared missions, skills, and resources that are common across all LS-RIs, offering harmonisation and unified frameworks. Simultaneously, a **federated network of CCs** would respect the autonomy of individual RIs, leveraging existing services and community-specific expertise, particularly in the short term. This hybrid model allows for both consistency and flexibility, adapting to the evolving needs of the life sciences research ecosystem.

Example 2: Federating within a thematic Hub Enabling FAIR Data for Biomedical Research

An example of the impact of EOSC-Life is in **genomics and rare disease research**. Traditionally, genomic datasets have been stored in isolated repositories, making cross-study comparisons difficult. LS-RI services help federate these datasets, allowing researchers to **access harmonised genomic data, imaging repositories, and bioinformatics tools** via cloud-based services. Additionally, EOSC Life services like **WorkflowHub** facilitate **reproducible computational analyses**, ensuring that methods used to study genetic disorders can be shared and validated by different teams ([Goble et al. 2020](#)).

Using LS-RI services, researchers studying rare diseases can integrate **clinical trial data, genomic sequencing, and patient registries** in a single environment, leading to faster discoveries of disease biomarkers and potential treatments. The **Life Science Login (AAI)** system further enhances accessibility by enabling researchers to securely authenticate and access multiple resources without redundant logins.

The impact of LS-RI services is evident in their use to **support large-scale biomedical studies**. For instance, European research groups analysing cancer progression have benefited from **centralised data repositories**, improving their ability to **correlate patient data with genetic mutations**. This infrastructure is also essential for **drug discovery**, where

AI-driven analysis of molecular structures is accelerating the identification of new therapeutic targets.

5.5. ESCAPE Scenarios

5.5.1. ESCAPE Scenario 1: Cherenkov Telescope Array (CTAO)

The [CTAO](#) (**Cherenkov Telescope Array Observatory**) project involves several telescopes of various sizes capable of detecting **gamma rays** emitted by different cosmic sources (supernovae, active galaxies, stellar black holes, etc.).

These telescopes are located in the Northern Hemisphere (Canary Islands) and the Southern Hemisphere (Chile). A rapid initial data processing and alert system is performed on-site to enable the telescopes to adjust their observations and capture as much information as possible.

At the end of an observation, data is transferred off-site and enters an automated processing workflow, as described below and depicted in Figure 7.

1. Data backup and replication with Rucio:

[Rucio](#) orchestrates the distribution and backup of data, using [FTS](#) to ensure efficient and reliable data transfers.

CTAO Example: Rucio copies the original file to two of the four available data centers (depending on their capacity) and then deletes the original file.

2. Data processing with Dirac:

[Dirac](#) automatically executes the appropriate workflows based on the files detected in each data center.

CTAO Example: When a raw file (DLO) is detected, several processing steps are initiated. This processing is essential to make the data usable for physicists.

At each step, intermediate files (DL1, DL2, DL3) are saved on tape or disk. Algorithms will continue to evolve and improve over time. It will always be possible to reprocess data using the DLO backups.

3. Managing data access with IAM:

The **Identity and Access Management (IAM)** generates a token from a user account to allow access to the [ESCAPE Data Lake](#), while controlling the level of access granted.

IAM supports different types of user accounts, such as university accounts, Git accounts, etc.

CTAO Example: IAM allows for the management of various levels of data access based on user profiles. Everything is fully configurable.

4. Data analysis with the VRE:

In this implementation, the VRE platform is deployed on Kubernetes, which is synchronised with a GitLab repository containing the VRE configuration parameters.

Users authenticate through **ESCAPE IAM** and access a **JupyterLab** environment, where they can load, analyze, and manage data. Tools such as [Rucio](#), [REANA](#), and [Zenodo](#) are integrated and accessible through plugins.

CTAO Example: The VRE provides physicists with access to DL6 data, which has undergone prior processing orchestrated by Rucio and Dirac. This allows them to design workflows and analyze their results directly within the platform.

This solution is currently being developed.

Figure 7 – Diagram visualising the automated data process workflow described above

5.5.2. ESCAPE Scenario 2: ATLAS Open Data analysis

Scenario: A researcher is performing an analysis on ATLAS Open Data at the LHC, leveraging the ESCAPE services through the VRE.

1. Accessing Data:

- The researcher uses [Rucio](#) to locate and manage large-scale ATLAS Open Data across distributed data centers.

- b. [FTS](#) ensures efficient and reliable transfer of the required datasets to the preferred computing site or platform for analysis.
2. **Preparing the Workflow:**
 - a. Through the [REANA](#) platform, the researcher structures a reusable workflow that incorporates input data, analysis code, and containerized environments.
 - b. This workflow is integrated with the [VRE](#)
 3. **Data Analysis:**
 - a. The analysis is executed on remote computing resources provisioned through the VRE.
 - b. The researcher benefits from access to tools and services provided within the VRE, streamlining the computational steps.
 4. **Publishing Results:**
 - a. Once the analysis is complete, the results, including datasets and workflows, are published on [Zenodo](#), ensuring they are preserved and openly accessible for future research.
 - b. Any custom software developed during the analysis is shared via [OSSR](#), encouraging collaborative development and reuse by other scientists.
 5. **Community Engagement and Standards:**
 - a. Outreach efforts, supported by the [ESCAPE Citizen Science](#) initiative, allow the researcher to share findings with the public, fostering education and engagement.
 6. **Reinterpretation:**
 - a. Researchers can use ATLAS Open Data within the [VRE](#) to recast original analyses, testing a broader range of new physics theories than would be feasible within the experimental collaborations alone. This reinterpretation process allows the community to provide detailed feedback on existing analyses and propose innovative experimental approaches, fostering collaboration and exploring new directions in physics.

Role of [VRE](#): The VRE acts as the backbone of this workflow, integrating all services within a single interface. It ensures that data, tools, and computing resources are interoperable and accessible, enabling researchers to focus on their scientific objectives without needing to manage the technical complexities of service integration.

6. Conclusion and Next Steps

The aim of this deliverable, *D2.1 Clusters' Services and Data Sources Portfolios*, was to catalogue, evaluate and undertake a gap analysis of the Services and FAIR Data resources offered by the five [Science Clusters](#) in the domains of [Astronomy and Particle Physics](#), [Environmental Science](#), [Life Science](#), [Photon and Neutron Science](#) and [Social Sciences and Humanities](#). This work was undertaken in the context of the emerging [EOSC Federation](#), where the Science Clusters and their related Research Infrastructures play a crucial role.

Firstly, the deliverable provided an overview of the initial versions of the Cluster catalogues, which functioned as a baseline for the ongoing work to be undertaken as part of the OSCARS project. The first step in this work was for each of the Science Clusters to consolidate their catalogues and transition them to become *Services and Data Source Portfolios*. This process enabled the Science Clusters to assess the current status of their resource offerings, both internally within their own Cluster and comparatively across Clusters. A key outcome of this work was that the emerging *Services and Data Source Portfolios* were becoming useful tools, for both consolidating and managing their Cluster resources offer, as well as ensuring that it meets the needs of the research communities they are intended to serve. This researcher-focused approach complemented the work that was undertaken to initially explore potential *Composability Scenarios* for each of the Clusters.

This work in OSCARS WP2, has enabled the Research Infrastructures (RIs) as part of the five Science Clusters, to move beyond a primarily RI-focused approach towards a more Cluster-based approach of resource management. Additionally, it became clear that there are various approaches and levels of maturity to Cluster Services and Data Source portfolio management - *from manual curation, via collaboratively curated Cluster catalogues to cluster-wide knowledge graphs* - the opportunity to consolidate, compare and contrast these approaches, as well as exchange knowledge and experience, was considered very valuable by the Clusters. A key realisation from this work is that this Services and Data Source portfolio management will continue throughout the project, and potentially beyond, as part of the day-to-day activities of each of the Science Clusters.

Finally, the WP2 team agreed to bring forward the work related to composability, as a way of highlighting the importance of taking a researcher-focused infrastructural approach. Each Cluster undertook initial explorations of possible *Composability Scenarios* which can be further iterated in future stages of the project. These scenarios help to ensure the value of this work for research communities the Cluster's serve.

The work of this deliverable provides a solid foundation for the next steps that will be undertaken in the upcoming tasks as part of OSCARS WP2. Firstly, this will involve identifying where upgrades to the selected services may be needed to enable composability. This step will help ensure that the Science Clusters and EOSC more broadly, continue as

researcher-focused infrastructures. Secondly, the importance of considering the sustainability of this work from the outset has been emphasised. It is proposed that the [Be Sustainable Model](#), developed in the context of Life Sciences' Cluster, could be a good basis to explore its wider applicability and usefulness across all the Science Clusters. Finally, the Science Clusters are aware that OSCARS is being undertaken in the context of the emerging [EOSC Federation](#). With this in mind, it is important that both the *Cluster Services and FAIR Data Source Portfolios* and the *Composability Scenarios* are developed within the broader framework of the EOSC service offer, both at the level of the [EOSC EU Node](#) and the emerging *Candidate Nodes*, which together will form the basis of the EOSC Federation. Already the Science Clusters have been proactively contributing to the [build-up phase of the EOSC Federation](#) and any work undertaken in OSCARS needs to take these efforts into account.

In the coming months, the focus of WP2 will turn to the task of improving selected services to enable their composability, whilst supporting diversity of research practices.. The Clusters will identify and select a set of services which, when improved, will provide the basis for their **Composable Open Data and Analysis Services (CODAS)**. A first step in this process, will be the development of a **Composability Action Plan** (MS 6), where each Cluster will contribute to a shared document outlining the planned work. This work will provide the basis for organising a **Composability Workshop** (MS7) in September 2025, the aim of which will be to review progress on composability development and deployment, as well as explore initial ideas for engagement activities. A key contribution to this work will be exploring how the Science Clusters will engage with and support the research of the [projects funded under the OSCARS Open Calls](#). This work will be kick-started at the [first OSCARS Annual General Meeting](#), which will take place in Rome in March 2025.

Finally, the goal of this deliverable - *D2.1 Clusters' Services and Data Sources Portfolios* - was to highlight possible common approaches, foster knowledge exchange between the Science Clusters and identify where the EOSC services can facilitate the composability of these offerings. This deliverable has not only achieved this stated goal, but it also provides a solid foundation for the ongoing work on *composability* and *engagement* which will continue in WP2.